

Calibrating the Cepheid distance scale with Gaia

Louise Breuval

LESIA, Observatoire de Paris, Meudon, France

Cepheids are pulsating variable stars which play a key role as primary distance indicators thanks to the empirical relation between their pulsation period and intrinsic luminosity, the period-luminosity (PL) relation (or Leavitt law [1]). This law is used to calibrate the brightness of type-Ia supernovae (SNe Ia) in nearby galaxies, which is in turn used to measure the distance to galaxies in the Hubble flow. This provides an estimate of the current expansion rate of the Universe, the Hubble constant (H_0). In recent years, a significant tension of at least 4σ has arisen between the early universe measurement of H_0 from the Planck satellite, assuming a Λ CDM model [2], and the late universe direct measurements based on Cepheid distances [3]. The persistence of this tension would imply new physics beyond the standard model of cosmology: it is therefore critical to improve the period-luminosity calibration with precise and reliable Cepheid distance measurements.

Calibration of the PL relation with Gaia parallaxes

The *Gaia* mission is dedicated to measure the distance to more than 1.5 billion stars using the method of the parallax and constitutes an essential tool for the calibration of the PL relation. However, Cepheid parallaxes suffer from several systematic effects. *Gaia* Data Release 2 (DR2) parallaxes are subject to a zero-point offset which value is debated. Additionally, Cepheids undergo color changes during their pulsation cycle which produces additional noise in the astrometric data. Finally, the brightness of Cepheids often results in the saturation of the detectors and therefore in unreliable parallaxes for a large number of these stars.

In order to overcome these issues, we proposed an original approach based on companion stars and open clusters hosting Cepheids [4]. The astrometric solution of fainter and stable neighbour companions of Cepheids are more reliable than that of their parent variable star. Open clusters are also interesting for similar reasons: their numerous member stars allow us to derive an average value of the cluster parallax, which provides an alternative way to measure a precise distance to the Cepheids they host. In [4], we assumed a *Gaia* DR2 parallax zero-point of -0.046 ± 0.015 mas, which covers most of the estimates from the literature, and we adopted the *Gaia* DR2 parallaxes of 22 Cepheid companions and 14 open clusters hosting Cepheids to calibrate the PL relation in the optical and near-infrared (NIR). The dispersion of the PL relation obtained with this method is significantly reduced compared with using directly the *Gaia* DR2 parallaxes of Cepheids.

Recently, more precise parallaxes were published in the *Gaia* Early Data Release 3 (EDR3). The parallax zero-point can be estimated for each star individually and

takes into account the magnitude, the color and the position of the sources. Moreover, the longer time coverage of *Gaia* EDR3 seems to reduce the contamination of the astrometry due to variability that was present in *Gaia* DR2. In [5], I concluded that Cepheid parallaxes are more reliable in *Gaia* EDR3 than in *Gaia* DR2, and even more precise on average than companions which are sometimes very faint. On the other hand, the precision reached with *Gaia* EDR3 for mean cluster parallaxes is twice better than individual Cepheid parallaxes: clusters are therefore excellent substitutes to Cepheids for measuring their distance (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: PL relation in the K_S band based on *Gaia* EDR3 parallaxes of companions and open clusters [5].

The PL relation has direct consequences on the Hubble constant since it is applied to calibrate SNe Ia luminosities in nearby galaxies, which are in turn used to derive the distance to remote galaxies at large red-shifts. In [5], I replaced the previous HST and *Hipparcos* parallaxes used in [6] by our sample of *Gaia* EDR3 parallaxes of companions and host open clusters. I re-evaluated the initial Hubble constant of 76.18 ± 2.37 km/s/Mpc obtained by [6] and anchored to the Milky Way to a revised value of 73.47 ± 1.77 km/s/Mpc. This result is lower than the original value but is also in better agreement with other estimates based on water masers in NGC 4258 and detached eclipsing binaries in the LMC and in M31 from [6].

Influence of metallicity on the PL relation

It has been demonstrated that the chemical composition of Cepheids impacts their intrinsic brightness. Therefore, the difference in Cepheid metallicity between galaxies in which the PL relation is calibrated and the galaxies hosting SNe Ia must be taken into account by including a corrective term in the PL relation.

To measure this effect, we compared the Leavitt law in the Milky Way, where Cepheids are metal-rich ($[Fe/H] \approx +0.08$ dex), with the PL relation in the LMC and SMC where Cepheids are more metal-poor than in our galaxy

($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \approx -0.34$ dex and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \approx -0.75$ dex respectively). In the Milky Way, we adopted the *Gaia* EDR3 parallaxes corrected for the zero-point offset. We also applied a quality selection based on the RUWE parameter provided in the *Gaia* catalog. For the Magellanic Clouds, we adopted the distances recently measured by [10] and [11] with a remarkable precision using late-type detached eclipsing binaries. We slightly corrected these distances to take into account the inclination of the LMC and SMC and therefore used individual distances to Cepheids depending on their position in the Clouds. In order to avoid the presence of outliers, we only select Cepheids within a radius of 3 degrees around the LMC center and 0.6 degree around the SMC center. For the SMC especially, which has a very elongated shape, it is not to exclude that Cepheids could appear projected along the line of sight but are actually located at shorter distance: these stars are identified by a larger dispersion with respect to the PL relation and are excluded by the application of a σ -clipping procedure.

Apparent mean magnitudes are derived from well covered light curves and are corrected for the extinction. By applying a Monte Carlo simulation to the PL calibrations in the three galaxies, we derived that metal-rich Cepheids are intrinsically brighter than metal-poor ones. This is equivalent to including a negative metallicity term γ in the Leavitt law. The metallicity effect in the V , I , J , H and K_S bands is represented as a function of wavelength in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Metallicity effect as a function of wavelength and comparison with the literature [8, 9].

The results of this analysis are presented in [7]. In the near infrared (NIR), we find a significant metallicity effect with $\gamma_K = -0.221 \pm 0.051$ mag/dex. In the opti-

cal, it is also negative but weaker with $\gamma_V = -0.048 \pm 0.055$ mag/dex. Our results agree well with the Baade-Wesselink analysis carried out by [8], although they derived a stronger metallicity effect in the optical and generally larger error bars. On the other hand, [9] obtained a metallicity effect consistent with zero and independent of the wavelength, based on a purely differential analysis between the LMC and SMC Leavitt law.

A slight trend is visible in our values represented in Figure 2, which suggests that the metallicity effect is stronger (in absolute sense) in the NIR than in the optical. This trend should be confirmed by studying the metallicity effect on a wider range of wavelengths, including more bands such as *Gaia* optical bands and *Spitzer* mid-infrared bands (see also [5]).

Perspectives

This study shows that the calibration of the Cepheid PL relation, although improved in the recent years, still needs to be refined, and that several systematic effects must be better understood to overcome the remaining uncertainties in the extragalactic distance scale. The publication of the next *Gaia* data releases should considerably improve the calibration of the Leavitt law by providing a better estimation of the parallax zero-point and by including a correction for the color variation that affects Cepheids. Precise metal abundance measurements for Galactic as well as Magellanic Cloud Cepheids are paramount, since most studies still rely on mean metallicities in the three galaxies, due to the lack of precision of the current individual measurements. Cepheids in Open Clusters are very promising thanks to their precise average parallax: this sample will be observed in the HST system for consistency with the measurements of extragalactic Cepheids in SNe Ia hosts, which should considerably reduce the systematics related to the photometric zero-points. Finally, the upcoming launch of the JWST is expected to resolve the crowding around extragalactic Cepheids, which will again help reduce the systematics and approach a 1% precision on the Hubble constant.

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Short CV

2018: Master in Astronomy & Astrophysics, Paris Saclay University, France
 2021: PhD in Astronomy & Astrophysics, Paris Observatory, France
 2022: Postdoctoral researcher, Johns Hopkins University, Baltimore, USA